

Moisture Diffusion in Honeycomb Core Sandwich Composites

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SUMMARY

Thermocouples and humidity sensors were embedded within the core region of a honeycomb sandwich composite panel. The panel was placed in an environmental chamber at a relative humidity of 55% and 40°C. Measured core humidity levels slowly increased due to diffusion of water molecules through the composite face sheets. Measurements compare well with a preliminary prediction obtained using a finite-difference analysis.

Keywords: sandwich composites, diffusion, adsorption, moisture content, durability

INTRODUCTION

The entry of water into the core region of honeycomb sandwich composites results in an increase in weight and can also cause structural damage (e.g., core-face sheet bond failures) due to freeze-thaw cycles that accompany changes in external temperatures. Mechanisms that lead to water ingress into the core can be roughly grouped into two main categories: direct entry of liquid water due to capillary-type action or indirect entry due to diffusion of water molecules through the composite face sheets. Water ingress via capillary action occurs due to structural imperfections such as matrix cracks. In contrast, ingress due to diffusion occurs at the molecular level and can occur even in the case of 'pristine' undamaged composite sandwich structures, albeit over long time periods.

This paper describes a preliminary study in which a pristine honeycomb sandwich panel was instrumented with thermocouples and humidity sensors embedded within the core region. The panel was then placed in an environmental chamber that maintained a relative humidity of 55% at 40°C. Core humidity levels were monitored continuously over several months, and were found to slowly increase due to diffusion of water molecules through the composite face sheets.

EXPERIMENTAL ASPECTS

Test Chamber

The environmental test chamber used in this study was built in-house and is shown in Figures 1 and 2. The chamber consists of a 23 cm x 46 cm x 94 cm (9 in x 18 in x 37 in) inner stainless steel shell housed within an outer 38 cm x 61 cm x 109 cm (15 in x 24 in x 43 in) steel shell. A 7.6 cm (3 inch) thick layer of Temperlite[®] insulation is placed between inner and outer shells [1]. A fan mounted within an insulated 10 cm (4 in) diameter duct is used to circulate air through the test chamber. Although not confirmed during the study, according to manufacturer's specifications the duct fan creates an airflow rate of 2.3 m³/min (80 ft³/min). Hence, the volume of air within the test chamber is exchanged roughly 20 times per minute. A resistance heater mounted within the ducting is used to heat the circulating air. Electrical current passing through the heater is controlled using a Micromega model CN 77000 series controller so as to maintain a user-specified chamber temperature. Temperatures were monitored using two type K thermocouples mounted within the test chamber roughly 30 cm (12 in) apart.

Excellent temperature control was achieved using this arrangement. For example, using a controller set-point of 40°C (104°), over the course of the 9-month test reported herein the average chamber temperature measured by the two thermocouples was 39.8 ± 0.5°C (103.6 ± 0.9°F), the average difference between temperature measurements was 0.88 °C (1.6 °F), and the maximum temperature difference between the two thermocouple measurements at any time was 1.6 °C (2.9 °F).

As shown in Figures 1, the air stream was passed through an insulated chamber containing a bath of distilled water, so as to increase the relative humidity of the circulated air. There was a gradual loss of distilled water within the system, because the insulated water bath and test chamber were not completely sealed to the atmosphere. Roughly two liters of distilled water were added to the bucket every 48-72 hrs. Two Ohmic Instruments type HC-610 capacitive humidity sensors were used to monitor test chamber humidity [2]. The humidity sensors were mounted within the chamber immediately adjacent to the thermocouples. Chamber relative humidity measured during a typical 48-hr period immediately following the addition of water is presented in Figure 3. As shown, chamber humidity levels were reduced when distilled water was added but recovered to a stable value in 2-3 hrs. Over the roughly 9-month test period reported here the relative humidity within the test chamber was 55.1 ± 2.6% RH.

Fabrication of Instrumented Sandwich Test Panel

The methods used to fabricate the sandwich test panel are summarized in Figure 4. A 1.3 cm x 28 cm x 28 cm (0.5 in x 11 in x 11 in) sample of type 410 Nomex honeycomb core was placed within an aluminum frame with overall dimensions of 1.3 cm x 30 cm x 30 cm (0.5 in x 12 in x 12 in). The outer aluminium frame was used to eliminate the

possibility of diffusion through the edges of the plate. Humidity sensors and type K thermocouples were placed within two circular “pockets” that had been milled in the honeycomb core (Figure 4a). Lead wires emanating away from the two sensor locations passed through the walls of the honeycomb core and aluminum frame. An epoxy was used to seal the lead wire passage through the aluminum frame (Figure 4b). Circular pieces of honeycomb were placed over the two sensor regions, such that total core thickness in these areas was returned to 1.3 cm (Figure 4c). Two 8-ply [0/45/90/-45]_s graphite-epoxy laminates were used as face sheets. The face sheets were produced using a 177°C (350°F) cure Hexcel pre-preg consisting of type M46JB fibers and M70 epoxy resin. The fully cured panels were bonded to both the aluminum frame and the honeycomb core in a second bonding operation, using a thin-film epoxy adhesive. The completed test panel is shown in Figure 4d.

The test panel was placed in the humidity chamber on 5 August 2008 and exposure to constant environmental conditions of 55% RH at 40°C (104 °F) began at that time. Measurements obtained over the first 258 days (~9 mos) of exposure are plotted in Figure 5. The initial core humidity level was about 24% RH, but after 258 days of exposure core humidity has nearly doubled to about 46%RH.

The intention is to maintain constant environmental conditions of 55%RH at 40°C for a 1-year period (i.e., until 4 August 2009). After one year of exposure the panel will be removed from the environmental chamber and dissected, which will allow precise measurement of the various physical dimensions present in the panel, such as ply thickness, thickness of the epoxy layer between face sheets and core, and thickness of the Nomex core.

MODELING ASPECTS

Moisture diffusion in pristine composite sandwich panels can be modeled using Fick’s laws of diffusion. For one-dimensional flow Fick’s first and second laws may be written:

$$\phi = -\frac{D\rho}{100} \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \right] = \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \frac{\partial D}{\partial z} + D \frac{\partial^2 M}{\partial z^2} \quad (2)$$

where:

ϕ = moisture flux, mass/area-time

D = diffusion coefficient, area/time

ρ = density, mass/volume

z = direction of diffusion, length

M = percent moisture content by weight

For polymers the diffusion coefficient D depends on both moisture content and temperature. For epoxies the dependence of D on moisture content is usually minimal and is often (although not always) ignored [3-7]. On the other hand, the diffusion coefficient is highly temperature dependent and follows an Arrhenius-type relationship:

$$D = D_o \exp\left(-\frac{E}{T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where:

D_o, E = material constants

T = absolute temperature

In contrast, the temperature dependence of the diffusion coefficient of water vapor in air follows a power law of the form [8]:

$$D_{air} = 21.78 \left(\frac{T}{273}\right)^{1.81} \frac{mm^2}{sec} \quad (4)$$

where the temperature used with Eq (4) must be expressed in °K.

The diffusion coefficient of water molecules in air is typically orders of magnitude higher than the diffusion coefficient of water molecules in polymers.

The Nomex honeycomb core region was idealized as a homogenous layer. The effective properties of the idealized layer were estimated using properties of the constituents (i.e., air and Nomex paper) and the rule-of-mixtures. Volume fractions of core air and paper were calculated using the unit cell shown in Figures 6 and 7. A honeycomb core is characterized by a repeating hexagonal pattern of cell size c , formed using a thin paper of thickness w . The repeat cell is a rectangular region with length and width of $\sqrt{3}c$ and c , respectively. Based on Figures 6 and 7 can be shown:

$$V_{air} = \frac{3c - 8w}{3c} \quad (5a)$$

$$V_{paper} = \frac{8w}{3c} \quad (5b)$$

where:

V_{air} = Volume fraction of air within the core region

V_{paper} = Volume fraction of paper within the core region

The effective density and diffusivity of the core region can then be calculated based on these volume fractions and the rule of mixtures:

$$\rho_{core} = V_{air} \rho_{air} + V_{paper} \rho_{paper}$$

$$D_{core} = V_{air} D_{air} + V_{paper} D_{paper}$$

Zigrang and Bergmann state that a rule-of-mixtures approach cannot be used to model the moisture adsorption of the honeycomb core material, since moisture transfer within the core region occurs from the entrapped air normal to the core ribbons [7]. However these authors were primarily interested in predicting the long-term moisture content of the core paper itself, whereas in this study the primary objective was to predict humidity levels of the air trapped within the core. For the specimen considered herein the volume fraction of air within the core exceed 97%, so for present purposes a rule of mixtures approach was judged to be of sufficient accuracy.

The moisture content of a polymer or polymer-based composite exposed to air with relative humidity %RH for sufficiently long times is given by [3-7]:

$$M = M_{max} \left(\frac{\%RH}{100} \right)^b \quad (6)$$

Note that the surface of a bulk polymeric sample is considered to develop the moisture content given by Eq (6) instantaneously.

Maximum moisture content M_{max} and exponent b are treated as material constants for a given polymer or polymeric composite and are determined based on a fit to experimental data. For epoxies the specific value of M_{max} depends on the particular resin/hardener combination used as well as curing conditions, but is usually 2% or less. Exponent b is usually equal to or greater than unity. It has been observed that a good fit can often be achieved by assuming the exponent is unity ($b = 1$), which of course affects the estimated value of M_{max} [6]. In the present study $b = 1$ was assumed.

Although moisture diffusion is governed by Eqs (1) and (2), a closed-form solution cannot be obtained in the present case due to the discontinuous change in properties that occurs at all interfaces between dissimilar materials. Hence, solutions are obtained using a finite-difference approach. Similar finite-difference methods have been used to predict moisture diffusion in sandwich panels by others [7], so a detailed discussion of the analysis procedure will not be provided here. Briefly, all derivatives that appear in Eqs (1) and (2) can be approximated in finite-difference form:

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial t} \approx \frac{M(z_i, t_i) - M(z_i, t_{i-1})}{t_i - t_{i-1}} \quad (7a)$$

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \approx \frac{M(z_i, t_i) - M(z_{i-1}, t_i)}{z_i - z_{i-1}} \quad (7b)$$

$$\frac{\partial D}{\partial z} \approx \frac{D(z_i, t_i) - D(z_{i-1}, t_i)}{z_i - z_{i-1}} \quad (7c)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 M}{\partial z^2} \approx \frac{M(z_{i+1}, t_i) - 2M(z_i, t_i) + M(z_{i-1}, t_i)}{(z_{i+1} - z_i)(z_i - z_{i-1})} \quad (7d)$$

Substituting Eqs (7a-d) into Eq (2) results in Fick's second law in finite difference form:

$$[-\lambda_i]M(i-1, 2) + [1 + \lambda_i + \lambda'_i] M(i, 2) - [\lambda'_i]M(i+1, 2) = M(i, 1) \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\lambda_i = \frac{(t_i - t_{i-1})D(i, 2)}{(z_{i+1} - z_i)(z_i - z_{i-1})}$$

$$\lambda'_i = \frac{(t_i - t_{i-1})D(i+1, 2)}{(z_{i+1} - z_i)^2}$$

Two additional conditions must also be satisfied at all interfaces between dissimilar materials, for example at the adhesive/core interface [4, 7]. The first condition is that the moisture flux leaving the adhesive layer must equal the moisture flux entering the adjacent core region. Since moisture flux is given by Fick's first law, Eq (1), this condition requires:

$$(D\rho)_a \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \right) \Big|_a = (D\rho)_c \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \right) \Big|_c \quad (9)$$

where "a" and "c" have been used to represent "adhesive" and "core", respectively. Equation (9) can be cast in finite-difference form using Eq (7b):

$$[\beta_i]M(i, 2) - \left[\beta_i + \beta_{i+1} \left(\frac{M(i+1)}{M_u(i)} \right) \right] M(i+1, 2) + [\beta_{i+1}]M(i+2, 2) = 0 \quad (10)$$

where:

$$\beta_i = \frac{D(i, 2)\rho(i)}{z_{i+1} - z_i}$$

The second condition is that the moisture content at an adhesive/core interface must be consistent with Eq (6). Recall that it has been assumed that $b = 1$ in this study. Hence,

at the interface the moisture content of the core (M^c) is related to the moisture content of the adhesive (M^a) according to:

$$M^c = M^a \left(\frac{M_{\max}^c}{M_{\max}^a} \right) \quad (11)$$

The analysis is arranged to allow the through-thickness step size, $(z_i - z_{i-1})$ to vary through the thickness. This accommodates use of a small step size in the face sheet regions, where diffusion occurs at a very low rate, and a relatively larger step size in the honeycomb core region, where diffusion occurs at a higher rate. A convergence study must be performed to determine the appropriate number of divisions for a given analysis. Numerical results presented in a following section were obtained using a step size equal to half the ply thickness (0.0635 mm = 0.0025 in) in the face sheet region, whereas a step size of 0.635 mm (0.025 in) was used in the honeycomb core region.

Equations (8)-(11) are used to generate a system of simultaneous equations that are solved simultaneously, subject to the initial conditions and prevailing boundary conditions. Initial conditions are established by assuming that moisture content is constant and uniform through the thickness of the panel at time $t = 0$. Boundary conditions are established by assuming that the two external surfaces of the panel are subject to air with a known temperature and % relative humidity. Hence, the moisture content of the surface layers of both face sheets can be calculated at any time t_i using Eq (6).

PRELIMINARY COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASUREMENT AND PREDICTION

A preliminary comparison between measurement and predictions is shown in Figure 8. The comparison is termed ‘preliminary’ because properties for the specific materials used in the panel tested which are needed for the finite-difference analysis are not available. Instead, the predictions shown are based on properties estimated from the literature, as summarized in Table 1. Note that properties associated with moisture diffusion vary from one material system to the next, so the properties listed in Table 1 should only be viewed as typical values. Predictions are also sensitive to the thicknesses involved. The thicknesses for Nomex core, graphite-epoxy plies, and the neat epoxy resin listed in Table 1 and used in the analysis were adjusted to achieve the fit shown in Figure 8. Actual properties and thicknesses will be measured in late summer 2009, after the 1-yr exposure time is complete and the panel is dissected. Still, the good comparison between measurements and numerical analysis apparent in Figure 8 demonstrates the validity of the finite-difference analysis model.

Table 1: Material Properties Used in the Finite-Difference Analysis

Property	Type 410 Nomex Honeycomb Core ^a	Graphite/Epoxy ^b	Neat Epoxy Resin ^b
D_o	8 mm ² /sec	6.5 mm ² /sec	16 mm ² /sec
E	5000 °K	5722 °K	5722 °K
M_u	0.03	0.02	0.02
ρ	0.00072 gm/mm ³	0.0015 gm/mm ³	0.0015 gm/mm ³
Core thickness	13.0 mm	N/A	N/A
Ply thickness	N/A	0.142 mm	0.127 mm

a) Properties estimated based on the measurements of Zigrang and Bergmann [7]

b) Properties estimated based on the measurements of Loos and Spring [6]

SUMMARY AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

A pristine honeycomb sandwich panel was instrumented with thermocouples and humidity sensors embedded within the core region and then placed in an environmental chamber that maintained a relative humidity of 55% at 40°C. Core humidity levels were monitored continuously since initiation of exposure, which began on 5 August 2008. Plans are to continue the test for a 1-year period, after which the panel will be dissected and inspected. Data collected during the first 258 days of exposure (~9 months) have been presented herein. The measured core humidity level has nearly doubled over the 258 day exposure period, from about 24%RH to 46%RH. The increase in core humidity is due to diffusion of water molecules through the graphite-epoxy face sheets.

In addition to an increase in weight, these results are significant because if a sandwich composite with high humidity within the core region is exposed to temperatures below the freezing point then water will condense and freeze within the core. This scenario is encountered during ascent to cruising altitudes for large transport aircraft structures, for example. This will result in a freeze-thaw cycle that may be detrimental to a sandwich composites structure.

Since only one sandwich panel has been tested to date, the results presented here are not statistically valid and are preliminary. Efforts to obtain funding to allow a broader and more comprehensive study are ongoing.

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Figure 1: Sketch of the environmental test chamber

Figure 2: Photo of the test chamber

Figure 3: Chamber humidity levels measured over a typical 48-hr period

(a) Thermocouples and humidity sensors

(b) Lead wire passage sealed with epoxy

(c) Circular honeycomb “caps” used to achieve uniform core thickness

(d) Completed sandwich panel with embedded sensors

Figure 4: Method used to fabricate instrumented sandwich composite test panel.

Figure 5: Core humidity levels measured over the initial 258-day exposure time

Figure 6: Repeating unit cell for a hexagonal honeycomb panel

Figure 7: Dimensions needed to determine volume fractions

Figure 8: Preliminary comparison between measurement and 2-yr predictions, based on estimated properties and dimensions